

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS EVALUATION OF HYBRID METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The objective of this study is to evaluate comparison of fracture toughness between static and dynamic behavior in various metal matrix composites(MMCs) fabricated by squeeze infiltration method. A lot of MMCs which comprise various matrix alloy, volume fractions, and types of reinforcements have been tested. Static and dynamic fracture toughness of MMCs remarkably increased due to the addition of ceramic reinforcements. Specifically dynamic fracture toughness was slightly decreased compared with static fracture toughness because of the dynamic loading effect. In this work, major effects which influence toughness could be include the type of reinforcement, volume fraction and combination of reinforcement, and the matrix alloy. And notch fracture toughness which is not produced the pre-crack was discussed.

KEYWORDS: hybrid metal matrix composites, squeeze infiltration method, dynamic fracture, toughness, static fracture toughness, notch fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been an effort to use discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites for engineering structural applications. These composites can offer distinct technological advantages over continuously reinforced MMCs including fabricability using squeeze infiltration method, as well as cost advantages[1-3]. A lot of studies on metal matrix composites(MMCs) have been done but there have been very limited structural applications so far since significant problems remain unresolved, such as complexity of processing, high costs, low fracture toughness and low strain to failure[4, 6, 7].

Many studies have been undertaken concerning the static fracture toughness of aluminum alloys with either SiC particulate or whisker reinforcement. Few studies on comparison between the static and dynamic fracture toughness behavior have been available in the literature. These have been done mainly on the fracture toughness of discontinuous MMCs reinforced by the addition of a single reinforcement, such as Al₂O₃, SiC, and C, etc.[2, 4 - 11]. However, little attention was paid to the effect of hybrid metal matrix composites on fracture toughness behavior. Moreover, reinforcement with a single fiber has been the major subject of research and development, while reinforcement with hybrid fibers which consists of two or more reinforcements has not widely been studied. Evaluation of fracture toughness of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites becomes important for application as structural materials.

In this study, therefore, the authors conducted the experimental study to investigate the fracture toughness behavior of hybrid MMCs, and also to compare the behavior of static and dynamic fracture toughness. In addition, the plane strain and notch fracture toughness for MMCs were evaluated to find the effect of notch at the crack tip.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials and Fabrication

For the fabrication of composite materials, various reinforcements such as alumina, SiC whisker and carbon fiber were used, and Al6061 wrought product and cast Al alloy of AC2B and AC8A were used as a matrix as indicated in Table 1. Typical specifications of reinforcements used are listed in Table 2 [13, 14]. After preparation of preform by vacuum equipment, and then we have fabricated the MMCs by using squeeze infiltration method. Casting ingots for mechanical and fracture toughness tests were given a T6 heat treatment.

Table 1. Specification of various reinforcements used

Material	Chemical composition(w/o)									
	Si	Cu	Mg	Ni	Fe	Mn	Zn	Ti	Pb	Al
AC2B	6.0	3.0	0.4	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.09	0.1	0.15	rem.
AC8A	12.7	1.1	0.9	1.57	0.8	0.1	0.12	0.15	0.04	rem
Al6061	6.0	0.2	1.0	-	0.6	0.1	0.2	0.1	-	rem

Table 2. Specification of various reinforcements used

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (mm)	Length (mm)	Aspect ratio(l/d)	T. S (GPa)	E (GPa)
Al ₂ O ₃	3.3	4	150	38	2.0	310
SiC _w	3.2	0.6	15	25	3~14	600
Carbon	1.9	16	144	8.2	1.9	280

Mechanical and Fracture Toughness Tests

Room temperature tensile tests were performed with a universal testing machine. Tensile tests were displacement controlled and the displacement rate was 0.5mm/min. To measure strains, an extensometer with a gage length of 12.5mm was attached in the center of the gage length to round bar specimen. Round tensile specimens with 6.5mm diameter and 65 mm length were machined perpendicular to the direction of the applied pressure.

Static fracture toughness test was carried out at room temperature according to ASTM E399 and 5ton capacity hydraulic testing machine was used. In the case of matrix alloy, we performed the CTS test using the single specimen J-integral test method according to ASTM standard E813. Dynamic fracture toughness test was carried out at room temperature and 300 J capacity instrumented Charpy impact testing machine was used. The fatigue tests for the

induced pre-crack were conducted under constant load amplitude with a R value of 0.1 using a sinusoidal wave form at a frequency of 10 Hz. Crack length measurements were performed using a traveling light microscope (with resolution < 5mm) on the surface of the specimens.

Using P_Q and P_m obtained from experiment, static and dynamic fracture toughness are calculated as followed equation (1) and equation(2), respectively.

$$K_Q = P_Q / B W^{1/2} \cdot Y(a/W) \tag{1}$$

Where, P_Q is 5% offset of maximum load , B and W are thickness and width of specimen, respectively, and Y (a/W) is configuration coefficient of CT specimen.

$$K_{Id} = P_m \cdot S / B W^{3/2} \cdot Y(a/W) \tag{2}$$

Where, P_m is maximum load after impact loading, and S is span of specimen, Y (a/W) is configuration coefficient of 3-point bending specimen.

a) Specimen orientation

b) Static toughness test specimen

Fig. 1 Orientation from cast ingot and dimension of fracture toughness test specimen

Test specimens were machined from cast ingots parallel to the applied pressure direction as shown in Fig.1(a) The static fracture toughness tests were performed on compact tension (CT) type specimens of 25 mm width and 12.5 mm thickness as shown in Fig. 1(b) and the dynamic fracture toughness tests were performed on 3-point bending type specimens of 55 mm width and 10 mm thickness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Fracture Toughness

The various manufacturing methods of composites currently in use dictate that large microstructural variations between different materials are to be expected. This means that fracture toughness behavior of MMCs might be sensitive to actual manufacturing methods, such as the squeeze casting and powder metallurgy route. Fracture toughness behavior of MMCs is associated not only with the matrix, but also affected by some other factors, such as type, size and orientation of reinforcement. Therefore, we have focused on effects of controlling a complexity interaction between the matrix alloy and reinforcement on fracture toughness of short fiber reinforced MMCs.

Table 3 summarizes the results of static and dynamic fracture toughness experimented. We have discussed in three types of metal matrix composites which is used each different matrix alloy as follows. In the case of AC2B based MMCs, firstly, plane strain fracture toughness (K_{1C}) of alumina and hybrid composites was decreased about 50% compared with that of matrix alloy. Comparison of fracture toughness values between Al_2O_3 -15%/Al and Al_2O_3 -12%/C-3%/Al composites were little different as showed 45% and 47%, respectively. We generally understand that mechanical properties of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composite are improved over matrix alloy because of the addition of ceramic reinforcement. Ductility of MMCs, however, decreases remarkably since ceramic reinforcements in composite restrain to deform a matrix alloy. Static fracture toughness of Al_2O_3 /C/Al composite showed greater than that of Al_2O_3 /Al composite. This results seem to be a similar tensile properties, in which elongation of Al_2O_3 /C/Al composite is improved over Al_2O_3 /Al composite. And ductility of alumina composite was decreased with the increase of volume fraction, so that elongation of Al_2O_3 -20%/Al composite was decreased up to 9% compared with that of Al_2O_3 -15%/Al composite. Consequently, reduction of ductility in composites resulted in the deterioration of fracture toughness.

In the case of AC8A based MMCs, static fracture toughness test was performed with notch specimen since AC8A matrix alloy with elongation of 0.3% was very hard to produce the fatigued pre-crack. Therefore, strictly speaking, fracture toughness of AC8A based MMCs must be defined as a fracture toughness (K_C) rather than plane strain fracture toughness (K_{1C}). The static fracture toughness (K_C) of Al_2O_3 -15%/Al and Al_2O_3 -20%/Al composites was decreased up to 27% and 38% respectively compared with that of AC2B matrix alloy. AC8A based MMCs, however, showed less reduction rate than AC2B and Al6061 Al based MMCs. This results are originated in characterization of AC8A Al matrix alloy which has a low strain to failure. It means that AC8A aluminum alloy is not proper to structural materials. Compared amounts of fibers, fracture toughness of Al_2O_3 -20%/Al composites was decreased by 17% over that of Al_2O_3 -15%/Al composites. The increase of volume fraction in MMCs indicates the decrease of fracture toughness due to a low ductility.

Al 6061 based MMCs deals with three effects including hybrid, volume fraction, and notch on their fracture toughness. As mentioned before, static fracture toughness of Al_2O_3 -15%/Al and Al_2O_3 -20%/Al composites was remarkably decreased compared with that of matrix alloy, and was decreased about 20% with the increase of volume fraction. Static fracture toughness of Al_2O_3 /SiC_w/Al hybrid composites showed 14% lower than that of Al_2O_3 -20%/Al composites. Consequently, Al_2O_3 /SiC_w/Al composites appears to be more effective in strength than Al_2O_3 /Al composites[12]. Fracture surfaces of Al_2O_3 /SiC_w/Al composites show a different

type from those of Al₂O₃/Al composites. Overall, the dimple size of fracture surfaces in the hybrid composite appeared much smaller than dimple size of Al₂O₃/Al composites. This fineness of microstructure in Al₂O₃/SiC_w/Al composites is more effective in strengthening than in Al₂O₃/Al composites. FCG rate curves in composites, however, exist over a narrow range of ΔK since the K_{1C} values of MMCs are substantially lower than that of Al matrix alloy. On the other hand, the notch fracture toughness (K_{1C,N}) of Al₂O₃-15%/Al and Al₂O₃/SiC_w/Al composites showed 9% and 13% greater than plane strain fracture toughness (K_{1C}) which is produced the pre-cracked at the crack tip notch. Consequently, notch fracture toughness was increased about up to 10% over plane strain fracture toughness.

Table 3. Results of fracture toughness for various composites

Materials	Fracture Toughness(MPa√m)			
	Static toughness		Dynamic toughness	
	K _{1C}	K _{1C,N}	K _{1d}	K _{1d,N}
AC2B	2	-	1	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -15%	16.7	-	18.8	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -10%/C-5%	1	-	19.5	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -20%	15.3	-	3	-
AC8A	-	4	-	1
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -15%	-	1	-	16.8
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -20%	-	1	-	2
Al6061	29.5	-	4	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -15%	17.8	-	26.5	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -15%(N)	-	5	-	27.0
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ /SiC _w (15%)	15.3	-	23.7	-
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ /SiC _w (N)	-	17.6	-	22.6
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ -20%	14.2	-	18.4	-

* N means the notched fracture toughness specimen

In consequence, it can be known that static fracture toughness of MMCs was closely related with the ductility of material itself, as well as volume fraction, types of reinforcements, and matrix alloy. This effect is associated with the more extensive matrix regions surrounding the larger diameter reinforcements which enhance the toughness by producing additional constraint on the fracture event through matrix plastic deformation. Our results are showed similar behavior to Flom and Arsenault[4]. They reported that crack initiation fracture toughness did not depend on SiC particle size and crack growth fracture toughness increases as the size of the SiC particle increase. And notch fracture toughness values show within 10% of the plane strain fracture toughness, K_{1C}. Our results agree with Crowe's results[7] which reported that the apparent fracture toughness fits the relation $K_{1C}(\rho) = K_{1C}(1 + \rho/2c)^{3/2}/(1 + \rho/c)$.

Dynamic Fracture Toughness

The fracture toughness must be evaluated under the dynamic loading condition, when the materials are used for structures such as a pressure vessel that are desired to a higher safety and taken into account of the dynamic loading effect. Dynamic fracture toughness should be needed to an effort to use discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites for engineering structural applications.

As listed in Table 3, we will discuss the dynamic fracture toughness behavior experimented, as follows. Fig. 2 shows a typical plot of relations between dynamic load vs. time after impact tests, in which the computer aided instrumented Charpy impact testing(CAI) system is used. From P_m of this graph and equation (1), we calculated the dynamic fracture toughness(K_{1d}).

In the case of AC2B based composite systems, dynamic fracture toughness(K_{1d}) of Al_2O_3/Al and $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites was decreased about 40% compared with that of matrix alloy. K_{1d} of $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ hybrid composites improves by 5% over that of Al_2O_3/Al composites. This results are well reflected in elongation of carbon hybrid composites, which is more effective in toughening than only alumina composites. The effect of carbon fibers on the fracture toughness characteristics in the $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites, however, appears slightly improved.

Fig. 3 shows the SEM photographs of (a) Al_2O_3/Al and (b) $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites at near crack tip after impact loading. The fracture surface morphology of Al matrix appears widely dimpled, a so called, ductile fracture. The fracture surface morphology of both Al_2O_3/Al and $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites appears to be similar. Specifically, the surface morphologies of

Fig. 2 Typical plot of relations between load vs. time for Al_2O_3/Al composites

$Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites are far less rough since Al_2O_3/Al composites does not contain carbon fibers. Fracture morphologies of both Al_2O_3/Al and $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites appear essentially unchanged. However, the dimple size of matrix clearly increases with increasing fiber size. This dimple pattern could be affected a fracture toughness for each material.

Fig. 3. SEM photographs of (a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ and (b) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}/\text{Al}$ composites

In the case of AC8A based MMCs, $K_{1d,N}$ of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites was decreased about 20 - 30% over matrix alloy. $K_{1d,N}$ of alumina composites was decreased with the increase of volume fraction due to a low ductility. And in the case of A6061 based MMCs, we studied Al6061 based MMCs on the effect of volume fraction, notch and hybrid. Firstly, hybrid effect of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}_w/\text{Al}$ composites on the dynamic fracture toughness resulted in the decrease of 10% than alumina alone. Pre-cracked dynamic fracture toughness ($K_{1d,N}$) and notch fracture toughness (K_{1d}) of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ composites are little different. These are indicated similar behavior to dynamic fracture toughness of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}_w/\text{Al}$ composites. Consequently, this means that loading speeds may not much affect dynamic fracture toughness behavior.

Fig. 4 shows relationships between static and dynamic fracture toughness for both (a) AC8A and (b) Al6061 based composites. As shown in Fig.4(a), the static fracture toughness of AC8A matrix and composites under quasi static loading rate of $1.23 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}/\text{sec}$ increases about 10% over those of the dynamic fracture toughness under fast loading rate of $5 \times 10^6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}/\text{sec}$. The results are also consistent with showing a rather large increase in fracture toughness accompanying higher loading rates. On the basis of Duffy's model[9], it can be described that the increase in fracture toughness at the higher rates is due to a combination of an increase in the yield strength and fracture strain at the higher rates. The dynamic fracture toughness of a alumina(Al_2O_3) reinforced aluminum alloy is found to decrease as the volume fraction of alumina increase. The dynamic fracture toughness of a alumina(Al_2O_3) reinforced aluminum alloy is found to decrease as the volume fraction of alumina increase. As shown in Fig.4(b), K_{1C} and K_{1d} values show a large difference as the ductility of matrix alloy increase.

Fig. 4 Relationships between static and dynamic fracture toughness for both AC8A and Al6061 based composites

From these results, fracture toughness (static and dynamic) behavior of MMCs is associated not only with the matrix, but also affected by some other factors, such as type, size and orientation of reinforcement. In addition, the fracture toughness of ceramic reinforced MMCs is controlled by a complexity interaction between the matrix alloy and reinforcement. No single parameter appears to be capable of describing the full toughness response of MMCs.

The poor toughness of MMCs derives from i) a low initiation energy for fracture as a result of their high elastic modulus and low failure strains and (ii) a low propagation energy. Also, it is important to choose fibers of reinforcements for the development of hybrid metal matrix composites whether effects of hybrid reinforcement is always improved all of their engineering properties or not. Moreover, it is possible to improve the fracture toughness of these MMCs by the use of higher failure strain reinforcements and by increasing the propagation energy by the introduction of additional energy absorbing mechanisms such as pull out and reinforcement and matrix debonding.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the characterizations of static and dynamic fracture toughness behavior in various metal matrix composites were evaluated. These results can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The static fracture toughness (K_{1d}) of MMCs is found to decrease as the volume fraction of alumina increase. Reduction of ductility in composites resulted in the deterioration of fracture toughness. K_{1d} of $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ hybrid composites slightly improves over that of Al_2O_3/Al composites. Notch fracture toughness ($K_{1C,N}$) of MMCs was increased about up to 10% over that of plane strain fracture toughness (K_{1C}). Major effects which influence toughness could be found the type of reinforcement, volume fraction and combination of reinforcement, and the matrix alloy.
- 2) The dynamic fracture toughness (K_{1d}) of MMCs is found to decrease as the volume fraction of alumina increases. Static and dynamic fracture toughness of MMCs remarkably decreased due to a low strain to failure. K_{1C} and K_{1d} values of MMCs

show a big difference whether the matrix alloy is ductile. The effect of carbon fibers on the fracture toughness characteristics in the $Al_2O_3/C/Al$ composites appears slightly improved. Specifically, dynamic fracture toughness of MMCs was slightly increased compared with that of static fracture toughness because of the dynamic loading effect. Notch dynamic fracture toughness ($K_{I,d,N}$) of MMCs showed insensitive to actual loading speed.

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